

Change Management and Organizational Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria: The Case of Edo State

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between change management practices and organisational performance of some selected food and beverages firms in Edo State, Nigeria. The aim is to determine the relationship between change management in terms of change implementation and organisational performance. In an era characterized by rapid technological advancements and shifting market dynamics, effective change management has become essential for organizations to maintain competitive advantage and achieve operational excellence. The study adopted a survey research design and gathered quantitative data through structured surveys distributed to managers and employees of selected manufacturing firms which are Guinness Nigeria Plc, Nigerian Bottling Company, and Seven Up bottling company in Edo State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 1,172 employees of the three selected firms. A Sample size of 298 was determined using the Taro Yamane's Statistical formula. The instrument for data collection, the questionnaire, was subjected to content validity and reliability tests. Cronbach's Alpha test produced a reliability figure of 0.8 indicating that the instrument was consistent. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was deployed to test the hypothesis of the study. The result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between change implementation and organizational performance of the three selected manufacturing firms in Edo State with the correlation coefficient of 0.610 and P-value of $0.009 < 0.005$. The study concludes that there is a statistically significant relationship between change management and organizational performance of the three selected manufacturing Firms in Edo state and recommends that management of the studied firms should ensure that employees have the necessary resources, skills, and training to adapt to changes. The study underscores the necessity for manufacturing firms in Edo State and the country in general to cultivate robust change management frameworks to navigate the complexities of the contemporary business environment. Overall, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge on change management by highlighting its critical role in enhancing organizational performance, while providing practical recommendations for practitioners in the manufacturing sector.

Keywords: Change management, organizational performance, manufacturing firms, productivity, employee satisfaction

Introduction

In recent years, the need for robust change management practices has become critical for the survival and growth of manufacturing firms worldwide, including those in Nigeria. This is especially relevant in the dynamic economic environment of Edo State, where firms face challenges related to market fluctuations, technological advancements, and changing consumer preferences.

A popular saying reminds us that change is the only constant in life, and this holds true for the business world. In today's rapidly evolving business environment, nothing stays static. The rate of change affecting businesses has been increasing steadily, with global markets becoming more volatile, particularly in recent decades (Tamunomiebi & Lawrence, 2020). This shift is largely driven by advancements in information and communication technology, as well as the increased democratization and liberalization of economies worldwide (Ali, 2020). Change has thus become a standard aspect of

business life, requiring managers' attention to ensure consistent business growth. For companies to stay competitive, they must be agile in responding to external changes.

Changes within and outside an organization can have immediate consequences on its performance, given the close connection between management and employees (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2020). According to Muchemi and Wakonyo (2020), rapid changes in customer expectations and technology mean that companies must effectively handle these shifts. Adaptability in managing change is essential for manufacturing firms to stay viable (Awiti *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, Ufua and Ogisi (2020) note that unpredictable economic and political climates, shifting societal values, intense competition, mergers and acquisitions, regulatory changes, and new legislation all contribute to an uncertain environment for businesses, demanding their readiness to respond and adapt.

Over the past five decades, the rapid growth of business has highlighted the need for change management to keep pace with this acceleration. Factors such as heightened competition, flexible business models enabled by new technology, and global economic progress make "change" unavoidable (Agbo, 2018; Aninkan, 2018). Ekechi and Umar (2020) emphasize that change has become an integral aspect of modern business, and organizations should be prepared to manage it to ensure continuous improvement and success (Onyiyechukwu & Joseph, 2020). Ofuoku and Ogisi (2020) caution that organizations that fail to prepare for change management may have limited longevity. Change, being inherent in life, poses a risk to those focused solely on the present or past.

Warrilow (2010) underscores that in a dynamic environment, effective change management strategies are necessary for individuals to embrace change positively and to enhance organizational contributions. He recommends choosing change strategies that align with both the situation and management's preferred style. Go and Pine (2005) argue that unpredictable changes in consumer behavior and technology underscore the need for effective change management, which is crucial for long-term survival. Mullins (2009) adds that economic and political uncertainties, evolving social perspectives, competition, acquisitions, technological advances, and government regulations create an increasingly unstable environment, necessitating flexibility and responsiveness. For a business to thrive in today's turbulent market, it must master change management, which has become essential for success. Although there is no universal approach to organizational change management, there is general agreement that change, whether triggered internally or externally, varies in its forms and impact (Balogun & Hailey, 2004).

Implementing change within an organization is fundamental to boosting employee trust and fostering their role in the change process, as noted by McEvily and Zaher (2009) and Burnes (2004). In Nigeria, many organizations overlook the role of employees in planning, implementing, and reviewing change processes, which negatively impacts change initiatives. Burke (2002) argues that organizations undergoing transformation need teams to lead the change process, with a strong commitment to change, especially from top management. Scholars have debated whether change is always positively linked to organizational performance (Appelbaum, 2000; Wright, 2005; Schuler & Jackson, 2001). While most studies support a positive relationship between change practices and performance, this linear view may be insufficient (Edwards & Wright, 2001). This research, therefore, investigates the impact of change management on organizational performance, focusing on selected manufacturing firms in Edo State.

Manufacturing firms operate in a rapidly changing environment marked by technological advancements, evolving consumer demands, and global competition. To remain competitive and sustain growth, these firms must continually adapt to new processes, technologies, and market conditions. However, implementing change within these firms often faces significant challenges, including employee resistance, lack of effective communication, and misalignment with organizational goals. Poorly managed change initiatives can lead to decreased productivity, employee dissatisfaction, and, ultimately,

a decline in organizational performance.

While change management is widely recognized as a critical factor in organizational success, its impact on the performance of manufacturing firms has not been extensively studied. The relationship between effective change management practices, such as clear communication, employee involvement, leadership support, and continuous monitoring, and improved organizational performance metrics, including productivity, profitability, and employee engagement, remain unclear.

This study seeks to investigate how change management practices affect the organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Edo State. By identifying key change management strategies and examining their influence on performance outcomes, this research aims to provide insights that can help manufacturing firms navigate change more effectively, enhance organizational performance, and maintain a competitive edge in the industry.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Change is inevitable, unavoidable and necessary process of becoming different to achieve stated objectives of the organization. Change management refers to the structured approach to transitioning individuals, teams, and organizations from a current state to a desired future state (Kotter, 1996). The concept encompasses various practices, including effective communication, employee involvement in the change process, training, and development, which are crucial for enhancing organizational performance (Burnes, 2004).

Nowadays, organizations have realized the essence of change management practices. Daniel (2019) defined change management as a process that involves the unfreezing, moving and refreezing values, practices and procedures within an organization. It is a systematic and organized application or approach (in organizational structure, leadership, culture and technology) that determines employees' organizational changes from a particular state to desired future state. The roles of managers during change in an organization are: communicator, advocate, coach, liaison and resistance (Ekechi & Umar, 2020).

Kimhi, *et al* (2019) defined change management as a necessary process of defining and adopting corporate strategies, structure, technologies and procedures to deal with changes in external conditions and business environment. Change management is a systematic process of dealing with perspective change of an individual and organizations. It is a systematic and organized application or approach that determines employees' organizational changes from a particular state to desired future state. Nwinyopugi (2018) defines change management as the continuous process of aligning an organization with its marketplace and doing it more responsively and effectively than competitors. Change management process is a systematic approach to transitioning individuals, teams, and organizations from their current state to a desired future state. It involves a set of processes, tools, and techniques designed to effectively plan, implement, and manage change within an organization (Daniel, *et al*; 2019). Organizational change is the process of planning, implementing, and guiding change within the organization to minimize or avoid disruption and help employees adapt effectively.

Organisational Performance Metrics

Literature exposes the positions of researchers who have often postulated that organizational performance can effectively be assessed using indicators such as productivity, employee satisfaction, financial performance, and operational efficiency (Kaplan & Norton, 1992). Understanding these metrics is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of change management strategies.

Onyema and Onuoha (2020) defined organizational performance as a multi-dimensional construct whose measurement varies depending on several factors. It is an important aspect for every organization

whether it is a profit-making or a non-profit-making entity. It is the extent to which an organization as a social system with the resources and means at its disposal fulfils its objectives without incapacitating its means and resources and without placing undue strain upon its members.

Shariff, et al (2020) noted that organizational performance is positively impacted by the presence of change management practices. Change management tends to create a significant contribution to organizational competencies, and in turn, becomes a great advance for further enhancing innovativeness. Performance may be measured using different metrics such as revenue, profitability, customer count, staff counts, market segment occupancy, and even sales volume. Irrespective of the metrics, several factors influence the level of performance.

Theoretical Framework

Change Management Theories

Several theories underpin change management practices, including the Burke-Litwin Model of organizational performance and change, which emphasizes the “causal effect”. Since this model provides a foundational understanding of how the internal and external factors of an organization impact organizational performance, these researchers have adopted this model for the study.

The study is anchored on Burke-Litwin Model

The Burke-Litwin Model of Organizational Performance and Change, also known as the Causal Model, proposes a framework that links how internal and external factors impact organisational performance (Burke, 1992). Developed by Warner Burke and George Litwin in 1992, this model identifies twelve key dimensions within an organisation, showing how these dimensions interact and drive change. The model is valuable in assessing organisational and environmental factors critical to achieving successful change by emphasising causal relationships between them. The model explains that changes in one area, such as the external environment, leadership, or organizational culture, can create ripple effects across other areas, influencing overall performance. According to Martins and Coetzee (2019), the causal model effectively connects practical insights with theoretical knowledge, making it a valuable tool for understanding and managing organizational change.

Moreover, the Burke-Litwin Model serves as a framework for organizational diagnosis, facilitating both planned and managed change. Clarifying cause-and-effect relationships helps organizations understand which factors are most influential, with key drivers of change ranked by importance. Typically, the model's diagram places the most impactful factors at the top, illustrating how the external environment, for example, exerts a broad influence on internal dynamics (Burke & Noumair, 2015).

The Burke-Litwin model ideally presents how the combined framework consisting of external environment, strategy and mission, culture in the organization, organizational structure, practices by management, systems, climate in the work unit, jobs and skills of individuals, needs of individuals and values as well as motivation are likely to influence both Individual and organizational performance. The model will be critical to the current study as it will guide the assessment of leadership, organisational learning, and stakeholder involvement. In particular, the study suggests a cause-and-effect relationship between change management strategies such as leadership on performance of the organization. Of essence to state, the researcher will be seeking to determine the extent to which the propositions of the model hold to the effect of each of change management variables on the organizational performance.

Empirical Review

Several local and foreign researchers have done appreciable number of empirical works on the effect of change management and organisational productivity using various variables. Most of the findings of these research works suggest a positive statistical relationship between them. For example: Orishede, *et. al.* (2024) examined the relationship between change management process and organizational

performance of selected telecommunication firms in Nigeria using a purposive sampling method of survey design to collect seventy-five (75) employees from the employees of MTN, GLO and Airtel. To measure change management process (independent variable), the study employed “prepare for change” (PC), “create a vision for change” (CVC) and “implement change” (IC) as proxies while “Organizational Performance” (ORGP), the dependent variable remained as such. Questionnaire was obtained from respondents using five (5) Likert scale. Data were analyzed via descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The study found that there is a significant positive relationship between PC and ORGP ($0.048 < 0.05$); there is a significant positive relationship between CVC and ORGP ($0.000 < 0.05$); and IC has a significant positive relationship with ORGP which is evident with the p-value ($0.0038 > 0.05$). The study concludes that change management has significant positive effect on organizational performance of the selected telecommunication firms in Nigeria.

Agama, et al (2023) investigated the impact of organizational change performance of some selected construction firms. The population consists of the executives and employees of five Nigerian construction companies which are Phefa Construction Company Ltd., Abacus Building Services, Dumez Nigeria Plc, Enerco Nigeria Limited, and RCC Construction Company. The choice of these firms, according to the researchers, was based on some criteria such as the vintage of being included on the Federation of Construction Industry’s list (FOCI), size, active projects, geographic spread, and service portfolio. The total staff population of the chosen firms is approximately 1204 and the stratification technique was first used to stratify the workers. Taro Yamane was used to draw a sample of 300 respondents, who were then statistically tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The study found, among other things, a significant link between resistance to change and performance; critical factors for managing change will affect Performance; and change implementation will affect the performance of selected construction firms. Based on this, it was suggested that organizations should identify the best change model for their own initiatives and then modify to fit the context. Organisations should collect data from multiple sources, especially when assessing competency gaps, and employees should take management-organized training programmes seriously.

Akunne and Ibrahim (2021) worked on an evaluation of the impact of change management on employee performance in the Nigerian electricity regulatory commission. This research is aimed at evaluating the extent to which change management impacts on employee’s performance in the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission Sector. The study was based on data collected through questionnaire survey distributed to electronically to 80 employees the Commission out of which 60 completed questionnaires were returned making a response rate of 75%. Non-probability sampling techniques were used. Using descriptive and inferential statistical methods, they found that a positive relationship existed between various changes in the Commission, the attitude of employees to work and their general performance.

Fadila and Umar (2021) used the MTN Nigeria Plc to look at how change management affects the success of an organization in Nigeria. As a survey method, structured online questions were sent to 300 MTN employees out of a total population of 1000 using a simple random sampling method. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to look at the data. The results of the study show that changes in technology have a big, good impact on MTN's performance. Secondly, this study found that changes in customer tastes have a big, good effect on their buying habits. Finally, it was discovered that changes in leadership have a big, good effect on how well MTN employees do their jobs. This means that change management is a strong factor in how well an organization does its job. As a result, this study suggested that people in charge of change should always be ready for the big and fast changes that happen in business. They should use change strategies that are tailored to each organization to avoid the pushback that is likely to happen and improve the performance of the organization.

Udeme and Umar (2021) looked at how change management affected the work performance of employees in Nigeria. The research method used for this study was a descriptive survey. The Burke-Litwin model of organizational change was used for the study because it shows how variables affect both individual and group success. There are 1,400 staff members from Nile University of Nigeria Abuja, both academic and non-academic. Stratified random sampling was used to pick 311 people from the whole community as the sample size. The results from a five-point Likert scale structured questionnaire were looked at using regression analysis. Changes in organizational structure influence the quality-of-service delivery by employees at Nile University of Nigeria. There was also a link between changes in technology and the quality-of-service delivery by employees at Nile University of Nigeria, though it's not a strong one. When the leaders at Nile University of Nigeria change, it has a big effect on the quality of the work outcomes of the University's employees. Human resources are an important part of any business and can give it a competitive edge.

Olajide (2019) empirically examined change management and its effects on organizational performance of Nigerian telecoms industries using total of 300 staffs of Airtel randomly selected staff. Data was analysed using One-way Analysis of Variance. The result revealed that technology change has a significant effect on performance and that change in customer taste has a significant effect on customer's patronage. The result also shows that leadership change in management has a significant effect on employee's performance. The study therefore concludes that nothing remain still in the world of business as change is the only thing that is constant.

Similarly, Noble (2019) assessed the extent of employee involvement in the change management processes; assess the impact of change management on employee job satisfaction and thirdly, attitude of employees after organizational change. A descriptive survey research design was employed to administer a self-designed questionnaire to one hundred and forty respondents using simple random sampling. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics. The main findings indicated that employees' involvement in the process was limited to provision of adequate information. It was also revealed that generally, the change had a positive impact on employees' job satisfaction. Finally, employee attitudes after the change were found to be positive. Interestingly, respondents disagreed with the issue of high level of trust after the change process.

Okeke, et. al. (2019) examined change management and organizational performance in manufacturing companies in Anambra state, Nigeria. Their study was anchored on organizational change underpinned by the Lewin's Three Step Model. The study adopted the descriptive survey design using 286 employees working at the selected manufacturing companies in Anambra State as sample through the questionnaire. The study found that technological changes have a positive significant effect on organizational performance in manufacturing companies. They found that change management strategies have a positive significant effect on organizational performance in manufacturing companies in Anambra state. Specifically, the study found that leadership changes have a positive significant influence on organizational performance in manufacturing companies in Anambra state. It was the considered opinion of the authors that organizations that implement new technology should provide proper training to their employees to increase their performance. The reason is that every organization that builds strong organizational management strategies help to build good relationships based on their values, norms, behaviours, and perceptions. This is because leadership has the capacity to change leaders' mind-set, style, and behaviour as the change process they design because of their orientation must be such that can encourage employees to want to participate, to choose to contribute, rather than force them to do so.

Igwe et al (2018) investigated the effectiveness of change management and the level of commitment of top management of manufacturing firms in Southeastern Nigeria. Data were collected from two hundred and five (205) participant manufacturing firms who were financial members of Manufacturers

Association of Nigeria (MAN). 267 copies of questionnaire were distributed. Using Chi-square (X) statistic and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, the study revealed that change management improves the level of performance and that there is a very strong positive relationship between commitment of top management, middle management and success rate of implementation in the selected firms.

Hendrik, *et al.* (2018) examine the effect of change management, organizational culture and transformational leadership on employee performance. The research sampled 233 employees of PT Adhya TirtaBatam using path analysis qualitative method. The result of this study indicates that there is a direct effect of management change on employee performance; there is a direct effect of organizational culture on employee performance; there is a direct effect of transformational leadership on employee performance; there is an indirect effect of change management on employee performance through transformational leadership; there is indirect effect of organizational culture on employee performance through transformational leadership.

Nwinyokpugi (2018) worked on organizational change management and employee productivity in the Nigeria Banking Sector. The essence of this study effort is to investigate the consequence of change on organization and how best the consequences could be addressed to ensure that employees “productivity is enhanced. The study covers major banks and their branches in Rivers State and a randomized population sample of 152 respondents which comprise employees and management staff of these banks were drawn using Taro Yamen sampling formula. The findings indicates that all tested dimensions of organizational change management (Change Communication, Change Identification, Employees’ Engagement, Change Implementation and incentives) were significantly associated with the measures of Employees Productivity.

Methodology

This study employed a mixed-method (descriptive survey) research design to provide a comprehensive analysis of the impact of change management on organisational performance. The research targeted three manufacturing firms using the structured questionnaire. The targeted or selected manufacturing firms and their separate populations are: Guinness Nigeria Plc (712), Nigerian Bottling Company (272), and Seven Up Bottling company (188). Therefore, the population of the study was 1,172. To determine the sample size for the study, we applied the Taro Yamane’s Statistical formula and obtained a sample size of 298 respondents. Thus, the questionnaire was administered to 298 respondents on stratified basis while the selection of a specific respondent was on the simple random basis. Validity and reliability of data collection instrument were conducted yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.81 which is higher than the benchmark of 0.70 as recommended by Suwannoppharat and Kaewsa (2015). The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was deployed in testing the hypothesis.

Results

The result from the test of hypothesis shows a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.61 suggesting that there is a positive correlation between change implementation (as a proxy for change management) and employee engagement as a proxy for organizational performance. The positive sign indicates that effective change management practices are associated with higher levels of employee engagement. The p-value of 0.009 is statistically significant (typically, $p < 0.05$ is considered significant), meaning that there is a low probability that this correlation occurred by chance. Therefore, it can be confidently stated that a meaningful relationship exists between the two variables in this context.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of previous research (see for example, Agama, *et al.* (2023); Agbo (2018); Awiti, *et al.* (2020); Burnes (2004) underscores the importance of effective change management in promoting organisational performance. The positive correlation between change management practices and

improved productivity and employee satisfaction highlights the potential for firms in Edo State to enhance performance by adopting structured change management strategies. From the analysis carried out, the result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between change implementation and organizational performance of the selected firms in Edo State with the correlation coefficient of 0.610 (61%) and statistically significant at P-value of $0.009 < 0.005$ significant level. This goes to say that change implementation in the three studied firms will not encounter the resistance of employees if only the employees are carried along in the implementation process of such organisational change. This is also likely to increase employee engagement that will result to improved organizational performance of the studied firms. This finding is in line with the findings of Akunne and Ibrahim (2021) who studied the impact of change management on employee performance in the Nigerian electricity regulatory commission and the study found that a positive relationship existed between various changes in the Commission, the attitude of employees to work and their general performance.

Conclusion

The study concludes that change management, specifically the way changes are implemented within the organization, has a significant positive impact on employee engagement. This indicates that when employees are well-informed, involved, and supported throughout organizational changes, they are more likely to remain committed, satisfied, and engaged with their work. Consequently, effective change management practices appear to contribute positively to organizational performance through enhanced employee engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. that the Management of the studied firms should ensure that employees have the necessary resources, skills, and training to adapt to changes. This reduces anxiety and helps maintain productivity and morale.
2. that the Management of the studied firms should actively involve employees in planning and implementation. Engagement in decision-making can improve buy-in and adaptation to new practices.

Implications for Practice

Manufacturing firms should invest in training programmes to equip employees with the skills necessary for managing change effectively. Establishing a participative culture where employees feel involved in the change process can mitigate resistance and enhance overall performance.

Contribution to knowledge

This study adds to existing knowledge by quantitatively validating the relationship between change management practices and organizational performance through employee engagement. Specifically, it demonstrates that effective change management can positively influence engagement, thereby supporting organisational objectives. Furthermore, it highlights the value of using employee engagement as a measurable outcome of successful change implementation. This insight can guide future research and practices by underscoring engagement as a vital performance matrix in change management studies.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies should explore the long-term effects of specific change management practices on organisational performance and examine the differences in impact across various sectors beyond manufacturing.

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